

Hydrogen Bonding Interaction of Organothiophosphorus Insecticides with Alcohols

TRILOCHAN MEDDA*, SAMARESH MUKHERJEE and SANTI R. PALIT

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science,
Jadavpur, Calcutta-32.

Manuscript received 20 June 1978, accepted 2 October 1978

The equilibrium constants and enthalpy changes of hydrogen bonded complexes of organothiophosphorus insecticides like parathion, methylparathion and fenitrothion with seven different alcohols have been estimated from the $\pi-\pi^*$ red shift and optical density measurements at the shifted peak. The anomaly in solvent effect on the electronic spectra of organothiophosphorus insecticides which occurs frequently when a polar solvent is used has been discussed. Steric effect exerted by the alcohols has got an important role on the hydrogen bond formation in the systems under investigation.

VARIOUS workers¹⁻¹³ tried to establish spectrophotometric methods for the detection and quantitative estimation of parathion with forensic interest. The solvent-effect on the electronic spectra of organothiophosphorus insecticides which occurs when a polar solvent is used may be interpreted in terms of hydrogen bonding effect. In the present investigation we have studied the interaction of organothiophosphorus insecticides like parathion, methylparathion and fenitrothion with several alcohols. We have followed the suggestion made by Chandra and Sannigrahi¹⁴ to account for the self-association of the alcohols in the estimation of equilibrium constants. Breedy and Kasha's¹⁵ method as modified by Chandra and Basu¹⁶ has been followed in the present investigation in calculating the stability constant of the hydrogen bonded complexes.

Materials and Methods :

n-Propanol, isopropanol, n-butanol and t-butanol were E. Merck reagents and refluxed with freshly ignited lime for four hours, then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and finally distilled before use. Benzyl alcohol, supplied by Societe des Usines Chinisques (France) was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and then distilled. The process was repeated twice and finally the dried ethanol was distilled just before use. Parathion, methylparathion and fenitrothion were obtained as gift samples from Bayer (India) Limited. Those were steam distilled and the poisons were extracted with n-hexane from distillate. The extracted n-hexane solutions were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and then the solvent (n-hexane) was evaporated off. The solutions were then made in the non-hydrogen bonding solvent, Merck's carbon tetrachloride which was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and distilled before use. The solutions were made gravimetrically and the spectral measurements were taken with freshly prepared solution on a Hilger uv-speck spectrophotometer using stoppered quartz cells at different temperatures, (a

temperature constant within $\pm 0.5^\circ$ being maintained by circulating water through the cell holder).

Results

The observed red shift in the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the organothiophosphorus insecticides with increasing concentration of alcohols (Fig-1) was utilized to calculate the equilibrium constant by determining the slope and intercept of an $[A]/(\bar{\epsilon}-\epsilon_0)$ vs $[A]$ plot (Fig-2) in accordance with eqn. (1) due to Chandra and Basu

$$\frac{[A]}{\bar{\epsilon}-\epsilon_0} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon_1-\epsilon_0)k} + \frac{[A]}{\epsilon_1-\epsilon_0} \quad (1)$$

using eqn (1) bearing the same notations as before¹⁷⁻¹⁹. The plots of $[A]/(\bar{\epsilon}-\epsilon_0)$ vs $[A]$ were found to be linear in all the cases. The optical density measurements were made at different alcohol concentrations at the peak of the complex species. The equilibrium constant values were calculated from the optical density measurements at different alcohol concentrations. The enthalpy change of hydrogen bond formation between the organothiophosphorus insecticides like parathion,

Fig. 1

* Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Calcutta-700 014.

methylparathion and fenitrothion with alcohols was estimated from the variation of equilibrium constant with temperature (Fig-3): The results are summarized in Table-1A, 1B and 1C). We have also found isobestic

points in the $\pi-\pi^*$ band of the organothiophosphorus insecticides in carbon tetrachloride ethylalcohol system. This indicates the existence of equilibrium between the hydrogen bonded and free species of the solute.

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

TABLE-1A
EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT AND ENTHALPY CHANGES OF HYDROGEN BONDED COMPLEXES BETWEEN PARATHION AND ALCOHOLS.
PEAK OF NON COMPLEXED PARATHION AT 268 nm. CONCENTRATION OF PARATHION = $4 \times 10^{-5} M$.

Shifted peak nm.	Temperature °C	Equilibrium constant M^{-1}	$-\Delta H$ Kcal/mole	pKa in water at 25°C ¹⁰ .	δ^* of R in R-OH ¹¹
Benzyl alcohol-parathion system					
276	25	0.781 ± 0.03	—	15.4	0.215
Methanol-parathion system					
	25	0.505 ± 0.005			
275	35	0.424 ± 0.023	5.76 ± 0.25	—	—
	45	0.281 ± 0.021			
Ethanol-parathion system					
	25	0.423 ± 0.021			
274	35	0.354 ± 0.025	5.48 ± 0.23	15.93	-0.100
	45	0.239 ± 0.026			
n-Propanol-parathion system					
274	25	0.345 ± 0.009	—	16.10	-0.115
n Butanol-parathion system					
273	25	0.302 ± 0.024	—	16.10	0.130
Isopropanol-parathion system					
	25	0.234 ± 0.008			
273	43	0.186 ± 0.008	4.73 ± 0.44	17.1	-0.190
	59	0.114 ± 0.022			
t-Butanol-parathion system					
	15	0.117 ± 0.024			
272	25	0.092 ± 0.008	4.08 ± 0.34	19.2	-0.300
	35	0.072 ± 0.012			

TABLE—1B

EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT AND ENTHALPY CHANGES FOR HYDROGEN BONDED COMPLEXES BETWEEN METHYL PARATHION AND ALCOHOLS. PEAK OF NON-COMPLEXED METHYL PARATHION=267nm, CONCENTRATION OF METHYL PARATHION= $4 \times 10^{-5}M$.

Shifted peak	Temp. °C	Equilibrium constant M^{-1}	$-\Delta H$ Kcal/mole	pKa in water at 25°C	δ^* of R in ROH
Methanol-methyl Parathion system					
	25	0.445 ± 0.005			
273	35	0.372 ± 0.026	5.55 ± 0.29	—	—
	45	0.244 ± 0.018			
Ethanol-methyl Parathion system					
	25	0.394 ± 0.007			
273	35	0.266 ± 0.025	5.29 ± 0.15	15.93	-0.100
	45	0.223 ± 0.001			
n-Propanol-methyl Parathion system					
272	25	0.322 ± 0.016	—	16.10	-0.115
n-Butanol-methyl Parathion system					
271	25	0.274 ± 0.026	—	16.10	-0.130
Isopropanol-methyl Parathion system					
	25	0.215 ± 0.01			
271	43	0.131 ± 0.014	4.68 ± 0.44	17.1	-0.190
	59	0.102 ± 0.010			
t-Butanol-methyl Parathion system					
	15	0.112 ± 0.006			
270	25	0.084 ± 0.009	3.49 ± 0.2	19.2	-0.300
	35	0.078 ± 0.017			

Discussion

The spectra shift in the $\pi - \pi^*$ band of parathion, methylparathion and fenitrothion were associated with the hydrogen bond formation between the hydroxyl group of the alcohols and the π -electron system of the benzene ring in parathion and other compounds. The formation of weak 1:1 hydrogen bonded complex between the alcohols and the organothiophosphorus insecticides is evident from the equilibrium constant values.

Since we have allowed for auto-complexation of alcohols and have considered the monomeric alcohol concentration in calculating the equilibrium constants, our results are believed to have quantitative significance, Table-(1A, 1B, and 1C) shows that the equilibrium constant values for hydrogen bond formation run parallel with the acidic strength²⁰ or proton donating power of alcohols and also with Taft's polar substituent constant (δ^*)²¹. Such a correlation between the acidity

of proton donors and the equilibrium constant of the hydrogen bonded complexes shows in an indirect way the contribution of electrostatic part in the overall strength of a hydrogen bond. The results also demonstrate the steric effects exerted by the alcohols under study.

It appears from the data included in Table-1 that the hydrogen bonding energy in the organothiophosphorus insecticide-alcohol systems increase in the order : Methanol > ethanol > isopropanol > t-butanol. Since concentration of the alcohols are not very large in the experiments and corrections were made for autocomplexation of alcohols it is quite likely that the calculated hydrogen bond energy do represent the energy of one hydrogen bond. In case we are interested only in relative values, comparison of the values for a series of alcohols will also probably be valid. From comparative study it was revealed that these three organophosphorus insecticides have got almost the same hydrogen bonding ability.

TABLE-1C

EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT AND ENTHALPY CHANGES OF HYDROGEN BONDED COMPLEXES BETWEEN FENITROTHION AND ALCOHOLS.
PEAK OF NON-COMPLEXED FENITROTHION 266nm. CONCENTRATION OF FENITROTHION = $4 \times 10^{-5} M$

Shifted Peak nm.	Temp. °C	Equilibrium constant M^{-1}	$-\Delta H$ Kcal/mole	pKa in water at 25°C	δ^* of R in ROH
Methanol-fenitrothion system					
	25	0.432 ± 0.031			
292	35	0.394 ± 0.024	5.13 ± 0.44	—	—
	45	0.274 ± 0.001			
Ethanol-fenitrothion system					
	25	0.381 ± 0.028			
271	35	0.330 ± 0.004	5.06 ± 0.24	15.93	-0.100
	45	0.231 ± 0.017			
n-Propanol-fenitrothion system					
271	25	0.302 ± 0.006	—	16.10	-0.115
n-Butanol-fenitrothion system					
270	25	0.251 ± 0.006	—	16.10	-0.130
Isopropanol-fenitrothion system					
	25	0.203 ± 0.014			
270	43	0.135 ± 0.004	4.06 ± 0.43	17.10	-0.190
	59	0.107 ± 0.003			
t-Butanol-fenitrothion system					
	15	0.097 ± 0.002			
269	25	0.072 ± 0.002	3.39 ± 0.16	19.20	-0.300
	35	0.067 ± 0.001			

It is hoped that the results of the present work on insecticides may be of help to toxicologists for identification and also for understanding the solute-solvent interaction of such insecticides.

Acknowledgement

The authors are very grateful to Dr. Mohon Jauhari, Director, Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Calcutta and Dr. Amar Chattopadhyaya, Junior Scientific Officer, Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Calcutta for taking keen interest and making valuable suggestions during the course of the investigation.

References

1. A. I. BIGGS, *Analyst*, 1955, 80, 279.
2. R. C. HIRST and J. B. GILARD, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 185.
3. A. IRREDAYASWAMY, *J. Ind. Acad. Fors. Sci.*, 1966, 5, 19.
4. L. P. KUHN and R. R. BOWMAN, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1967, 23A, 189.
5. Z. YOSHIDA and N. ISHIBE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1969, 42, 3254.
6. R. D. SRIVASTAVA and P. B. GUPTA, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1968, 24A, 373.
7. M. OKI and H. IWAMURA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 567.
8. P. J. KRUEGER and H. D. MATEE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1964, 42, 288.
9. A. B. SANNIGRAHI and A. K. CHANDRA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1967, 40, 1344.
10. E. OSAWA, T. KATA and Z. YOSHIDA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, 32, 2808.

MEDDA, MUKHERJEE & PALIT : HYDROGEN BONDING INTERACTION OF ORGANOTHIOPHOSPHORUS ETC.

11. Z. YOSHIDA and E. OSAWA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 4019.
12. B. GHOSH & S. BASU, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1965, **61**, 2097.
13. B. CHAKRABORTY & S. BASU, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1967, **46**, 950.
14. A. K. CHANDRA and A. B. SANNIGRAHI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 2494.
15. G. J. BREADY and M. KASHA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 4492.
16. A. K. CHANDRA and S. BASU, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **56**, 632.
17. S. MUKHERJEE, S. R. PALIT and S. K. DE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 1389.
18. S. MUKHERJEE, S. R. PALIT and S. K. DE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 2404.
19. T. MEDDA, S. MUKHERJEE and S. R. PALIT, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 910.
20. J. MURTO, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1964, **18**, 1043.
21. R. W. TAFT Jr., "Steric effect in Organic Chemistry" (Ch. 13) edited by M. S. Newman, John Wiley, New York (1956).